

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Low-Energy DMTJ-Based Ternary Content-Addressable Memory With Reliable Sub-Nanosecond Search Operation

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ABSTRACT In this paper, we propose an energy-efficient, reliable, hybrid, 10-transistor/2-Double-Barrier-Magnetic-Tunnel-Junction (10T2DMTJ) non-volatile (NV) ternary content-addressable memory (TCAM) with sub-nanosecond search operation. Our cell design relies on low-energy-demanding MTJs organized in a low-complexity voltage-divider-based circuit along with a simple dynamic logic CMOS matching network, which improves the search reliability. The proposed NV-TCAM was designed in 28 nm FDSOI process and evaluated under exhaustive Monte Carlo simulations. When compared to the best previous proposed NV-TCAMs, our solution achieves lower search error rate ($3.8\times$) and lower write and search energy (-73% and -79% , respectively), while also exhibiting smaller area footprint (-74%). Such benefits are achieved at the expense of reduced search speed.

INDEX TERMS Double-barrier MTJ, non-volatile TCAM (NV-TCAM), energy-efficiency, low-power.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ternary content addressable memories (TCAMs) are widely used in a variety of applications, including network routers and switches, domain-specific hardware acceleration, and fully-associative memory structures (translation look-aside buffers, caches) in state-of-the-art high-performance CPUs [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6]. Although the high-speed massively-parallel search capability of TCAMs has always been an attractive feature, the scaling down of CMOS technology has resulted in a dramatic increase of leakage power in conventional CMOS-based TCAM designs [7]. Consequently, lowering the TCAM standby power is highly desired,

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especially in battery-powered applications [7]. To this end, non-volatile TCAMs (NV-TCAMs) based on single-barrier magnetic tunnel junctions (SMTJs) have been proposed as a low-power alternative to conventional CMOS-based designs, primarily for applications characterized by infrequent write operations [7], [8], [9], [10]. However, due to the renewed interest in associative processors [11], [12], [13], [14], where write and search operations are equally frequent, write energy consumption is now becoming to be considered also critical [5], [15].

SMTJ-based NV-TCAM designs proposed in recent years include latch-based [7], [8] and voltage-divider based [9], [16] solutions. By utilizing differential sensing, the latch-based structure offers reliable and high-performance search operation [8]. However, such an approach tends

to be area-hungry, approaching the size of a conventional CMOS-based TCAM solution. On the other hand, the voltage-divider NV-TCAM option exhibits a more compact area footprint; however, it experiences larger energy consumption and higher search error rate (SER). Indeed, all of the above-mentioned design approaches are affected by search errors, mainly due to the low MTJ resistance ratio between the two possible states and the CMOS/MTJ variability. This can be partially counterbalanced by up-sizing the transistors at the expense of larger cell area footprint and higher power consumption.

In this paper, we propose a very compact, hybrid, 10-transistor/2-double-barrier MTJ (10T2DMTJ) NV-TCAM cell, suitable for reliable, sub-nanosecond, and energy-efficient search operations. As opposed to latch-based solutions, which require a larger number of transistors and MTJs [8], we have exploited a voltage-divider approach, where improved search reliability is assured by using a simple buffer based on dynamic logic, which acts as a driver to manage the match-line discharging. Since the MTJ switching current reduction leads to both energy and cell area savings, we exploited DMTJ devices [17], [18] instead of conventional SMTJs.

The proposed NV-TCAM was designed in the 28 nm FDSOI technology and evaluated under exhaustive Monte Carlo simulations at the 3σ corners. When compared to previous NV-TCAM solutions, our cell presents a lower energy-per-write/search operation (-73% – -79%), while exhibiting a search error rate of less than 3%. These results were achieved with a cell footprint of only $2 \mu\text{m}^2$, which is $4 \times$ smaller than the best state-of-the-art NV-TCAM solution.

To summarize, the main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Our NV-TCAM employs ultra-scaled DMTJs to enable energy-efficient write/search operations.
- The proposed voltage-divider-based NV-TCAM cell relies on a low-complexity dynamic logic network to reduce the search error rate (below 3% for TCAM words as long as 144 bits), while preserving a competitive cell area footprint.

II. PROPOSED NV-TCAM DESIGN

In this section, we introduce a 10T/2DMTJ voltage-dividing based NV-TCAM cell, which is targeted to achieve ultra-low power, high-speed, and reliable search operation.

A. DOUBLE-BARRIER MAGNETIC TUNNEL JUNCTION (DMTJ)

In order to assure low-energy operation, our cell design, introduced in the next subsection, utilizes DMTJs as storing elements. Fig. 1 shows the structure of the DMTJ device, where the free layer (FL) is sandwiched between two tunnel oxide barriers ($t_{\text{OX},T}$ and $t_{\text{OX},B}$), with two polarizing reference layers (RL_T and RL_B). When the magnetization of the two reference layers is anti-parallel, the spin torques coming from both sides of the FL constructively add to each other [17].

FIGURE 1. Structure of the DMTJ with two reference layers, and two free layers. At the right: the simplified diagram of the considered DMTJ, along with the switching transition from HRS to LRS, and vice versa.

TABLE 1. Main physical and electrical parameters of the DMTJ.

Parameter	Description	Value
d	DMTJ diameter	20 nm
$t_{\text{FL}1}$	Thickness FL 1	1.6 nm [19]
$t_{\text{FL}2}$	Thickness FL 2	1 nm [19]
$t_{\text{OX},T}/t_{\text{OX},B}$	Top/bottom oxide thickness	0.85 nm/0.4 nm [19]
J_{c0}	Critical switching current	11045 MA/m ²
HRS	High resistance state	34.9 k Ω
LRS	Low resistance state	11.4 k Ω
Δ	Thermal stability factor	57
TMR	Tunnel magnetoresistance ratio at 0 V	187%

Therefore, the total torque acting on the FL is enhanced as compared to a conventional single-barrier MTJ (SMTJ), thus lowering the DMTJ switching current. For improved data retention time, we considered a double FL structure (FL₁ and FL₂) [19]. Fig. 1 also shows the direction of the electron flow to allow switching transition from high-resistance-state (HRS) to low-resistance-state (LRS) and vice versa. In order to simulate the impact of the DMTJ devices, we extended our DMTJ Verilog-A compact model [17] to take into account the double FL structure. The model was calibrated with the experimental data reported in [19] and [20] by considering the DMTJ parameters shown in Table 1. Note that the electrical characteristics reported in Table 1 are consistent with the state-of-the-art projections for nano-scaled DMTJs [17], [21].

Note that DMTJ structures can be challenging in terms of fabrication process and reliability [22], [23], [24], [25]. The need for an additional RL in the DMTJ adds fabrication complexity including stack etching and compensation of stray fields [22]. Adding an assistance layer, as proposed by Hazen et al., improves the dynamic behavior and stability of the device, thus ensuring better cell retention and performance [22]. The reduced DMTJ switching currents lower the required bias voltage, thus reducing reliability issues [26], [27]. Moreover, the overall reliability issues can be mitigated by stack/process optimization and/or magnetic shielding [25].

FIGURE 2. (a) NV-TCAM array architecture. (b) Circuit diagram of the proposed 10T2DMTJs NV-TCAM cell organized in voltage divider and matchline switching network.

B. 10T2DMTJ NV-TCAM CELL

An NV-TCAM is a memory block that compares a query data word with the entire memory contents, with the additional capability to ignore parts of the stored data words during the comparison by supporting “don’t cares” (‘X’s) in addition to logic ‘1’s and ‘0’s searches.

Fig. 2 shows (a) the NV-TCAM architecture and (b) the circuit diagram of the 10T2DMTJ cell. The latter consists of two main blocks: the voltage-dividing network (VDN) and the matchline switching network (MSN). The VDN includes two DMTJs (DMTJ1 and DMTJ2) and three access transistors NE1, NE2, and NT. DMTJ1 and DMTJ2 are serially connected, with the magnetization direction of the RL_T of the two DMTJs anti-parallel to each other. Together, the DMTJs form the NV ternary memory cell. The access transistors isolate the NV cell from other cells in the architecture and guard the DMTJs from direct high bias voltages that could lead to a breakdown. The gates of the access transistors are connected to the enable signals En₁, En₂, and the ternary enable signal, T_{EN}. En₁ and En₂ control the write and search operations, while T_{EN} only enables the ternary functionality. NE1 and NE2 are connected to the bitlines/searchlines (BL/SL and $\overline{BL}/\overline{SL}$), thus forming a voltage dividing network with output V_X, which feeds the MSN.

The MSN features a dynamic-logic network composed of a pre-charge transistor (P1) and an evaluation transistor (N1), both controlled by the pre-charge signal (PC). A single transistor (N2) comprises the pull down network, providing the inverted output, V_Y, which is inverted by I1 to provide the

output voltage, V_O. To control the charge lost at the node V_Y due to leakage of the dynamic design, a keeper device (P2), which is controlled by V_O, is used. Finally, V_O drives the gate of an evaluation transistor (NE) to conditionally discharge the matchline (ML) when V_X (V_O) is low. This constitutes the only possible discharging path between ML and GND.

Table 2 shows the combination of the control signals during the write and search operations. The write operation is accomplished by controlling the direction of the current path through the access transistor (En₁, En₂, T_{EN}) and the write signals (BL/ \overline{BL}) applied across the VDN. To write logic ‘0’ (‘1’), DMTJ1 and DMTJ2 are set to LRS and HRS (HRS and LRS), respectively. In order to write ‘X’, both DMTJ1 and DMTJ2 are set to LRS and transistor NT is enabled by asserting T_{EN}. As shown in Table 2, the ‘X’ write operation requires two cycles. The write voltage (V_{write}) applied across the VDN stack should be high enough to switch between the DMTJs resistances. Fig. 3 shows the timing diagram of write operations for all the possible write conditions of Table 2.

Search operation comprises pre-charge and evaluation phases. During pre-charge (PC=0), the ML and V_Y are pre-charged to V_{DD}. In the evaluation phase (PC=1), the MSN drives V_O to V_{DD} or down to GND, depending on the V_X voltage level. In the case of a match (mismatch), V_O is ‘0’ (‘1’), keeping (discharging) the ML at V_{DD} (GND). The possible search conditions (see Table 2) are shown in the timing diagram of Fig. 4. Note that write and search operations share the same path, through BL and SL, respectively. Therefore, the search voltage (V_{search}) applied across the VDN, has to be

TABLE 2. Write and search operations of the proposed 10T2DMTJ NV-TCAM cell.

Signals					MTJ resistance states (Stored data)				Condition or logic representation	Timeframe per cycle	Matchline
Control		Write/Search			Initial State		Final State				
En ₁	En ₂	T _{EN}	BL/SL	BL/SL	DMTJ ₁	DMTJ ₂	DMTJ ₁	DMTJ ₂			
Write Operation											
V _{DD}	V _{DD}	0	V _{write}	0	HRS	LRS	LRS	HRS	Write 0	≥ 10 ns [†]	-
V _{DD}	V _{DD}	0	0	V _{write}	LRS	HRS	HRS	LRS	Write 1		-
V _{DD}	0	V _{DD}	V _{write}	0	Any	Any	LRS	Any	Write X (cycle-1/2)		-
0	V _{DD}	V _{DD}	0	V _{write}	Any	Any	LRS	LRS	Write X (cycle-2/2)		-
Search Operation											
V _{DD}	V _{DD}	0	0	V _{search}	LRS	HRS	LRS	HRS	Search 0	around 1 ns [‡]	Match
V _{DD}	V _{DD}	0			HRS	LRS	HRS	LRS			LRS
V _{DD}	V _{DD}	0	V _{search}	0	LRS	LRS	LRS	LRS	Search 1		Match
V _{DD}	V _{DD}	0			HRS	HRS	LRS	HRS			LRS
V _{DD}	V _{DD}	0	0	0	LRS	LRS	LRS	LRS	Search X	Match	

[†] During write operation: ensures a write-error-rate (WER) of 10⁻⁷.

[‡] During search operation: it mainly depends on V_{search} value.

FIGURE 3. Timing diagram for the write operation of the proposed 10T2DMTJ NV-TCAM cell.

applied for a short time period (more on this in Section III), and should be less than V_{DD} to prevent overwriting the stored data.

III. DESIGN GUIDELINES AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

We explored the effect of V_{search} and switching time (t_{sw}) on the probability of overwriting the DMTJs during a search operation. The search path of our TCAM cell includes two series-connected resistors depending on the stored data, i.e., HRS + LRS, LRS + HRS or LRS + LRS for stored logic '1', '0' or 'X', respectively. Therefore, different search currents can flow through these resistive paths. Fig. 5(a) shows the ratio between the search current (J_{search}) and the MTJ critical switching current (J_{c0}), and t_{sw} as a function of V_{search}. Simulation results are extracted for a single NV-TCAM cell at the worst-case condition, i.e., when the

FIGURE 4. Timing diagram for the search operation of the proposed 10T2DMTJ NV-TCAM cell. Search '0', '1', and 'X' operations are evaluated with respect to all possible stored values (Case 1-'0', Case 2-'1', and Case 3-'X').

stored data is 'X'. In this case, the lowest resistance path is present, and therefore, J_{search} can exceed J_{c0}, thus potentially causing unwanted switching of the MTJs. t_{sw} is evaluated for a very constrained switching probability (P_{sw}) of 10⁻⁷ [28]. From Fig. 5(a), we can observe that for the considered

FIGURE 5. (a) J_{search}/J_{c0} ratio and switching time (t_{sw}) related to the worst case condition (stored data = 'X') as a function of V_{search} ; $J_{c0} = 11045 \text{ MA/m}^2$ and t_{sw} assures a switching probability (P_{sw}) of 10^{-7} . (b) P_{sw} versus t_{sw} at a V_{search} of 450 mV. Search operation does not compromise the stored data if t_{sw} is small enough to assure a $P_{sw} \approx 0$ (refer to the highlighted timeframe).

range of V_{search} , overwriting the cell is not negligible, but the probability of occurrence is not negligible only when a relatively long search pulse is applied. This is confirmed by Fig. 5(b), which shows P_{sw} as a function of t_{sw} for V_{search} of 450 mV, which is used throughout our evaluation. By limiting the search time to 1.1 ns, we can ensure with almost 100% probability that the DMTJs are never overwritten during a search operation. Such sampling time approach has been also exploited in recent CAM-based accelerators [4], [29].

Note that a number of works have shown low-voltage, small-sized TCAMs/CAMs operating at 0.3 V and 0.6 V [30], [31], suggesting that our design operating at 450 mV is suitable for small-sized TCAMs. To enable larger sizes, our TCAM requires higher V_{search} operating values obtainable at the device-level (considering a different MTJ device) or circuit-level (sizing the MSN and VDN to obtain a good trade-off between mismatch and match operations).

The NV-TCAM evaluation is carried out using extensive Monte Carlo (MC) simulations using Cadence Spectre, a modified DMTJ Verilog-A based compact model,

FIGURE 6. Statistical distributions of the match and mismatch voltages obtained for a V_{search} of 450 mV. Results are from 1000 Monte Carlo simulations.

and a commercial 28 nm FDSOI process. The MC simulations take into account device-to-device process variations for both DMTJs and transistors. For this analysis, we considered the n -cell NV-TCAM architecture shown in Fig. 2. The ML, shared along the TCAM word, is connected to the matchline sensing (MLS) block, which evaluates the state of the ML at the end of a search operation. We considered different memory word lengths ranging from 16- to 144-cells, featuring a V_{DD} of 1.05 V. For a V_{search} of 450 mV, the VDN output (V_x) of a NV-TCAM cell exhibits the statistical distributions of match and mismatch voltages shown in Fig. 6. While the binary CAM match (red distribution) and mismatch (blue distribution) offer a large sensing margin, the 'X' match of the TCAM features an additional distribution (green distribution), which exhibits reduced (about 50%) sensing margins. To properly differentiate between match and mismatch regions, the NV-TCAM cell dynamic logic network needs to be appropriately sized. For instance, making the dynamic logic network faster (slower) helps to better distinguish the mismatch (match) case. Therefore, a good trade-off (i.e., proper sizing) between match and mismatch regions has to be considered.

Fig. 7(a) shows the reliability and performance results in terms of SER and search time (t_{search}), respectively, as a function of the word length for the Typical-Typical (TT) corner. The SER rises from about 0.5% to less than 2.5% with the memory word length increasing. The t_{search} results are obtained at the worst-case scenario, i.e., when there is only one mismatching bit in the entire word. Moreover, t_{search} is calculated at the 3σ corner, reaching an average latency of 588 ps. The sub-nanosecond search time values are well within the safe timeframe reported in Fig. 5, thus avoiding overwriting of the stored data.

Fig. 7(b) shows the SER for different corners. While skewed corners (Fast-Slow (FS) and Slow-Fast (SF)) present

FIGURE 7. Search error rate (SER) and search time t_{search} as a function of the NV-TCAM word length, operating at 1.05 V supply voltage and considering a search voltage of 450 mV. t_{search} is evaluated for the worst-case of a single mismatching bit. Results are extracted by 1000 Monte Carlo simulations. (b) SER for the different process corners for a 144-bit word CAM.

errors up to 27%, the SER remains below 4% for even corners (TT, Fast-Fast (FF), and Slow-Slow (SS)). We can observe that for a fixed sizing of the NV-TCAM cell, a tradeoff exists between the SER and the t_{search} , i.e., one can be reduced at the cost of increasing the other. This can be accomplished by changing the V_{search} , for instance, in the range of 400 mV to 500 mV. Higher V_{search} allows faster switching but compromises the stored data and SER. On the contrary, lower V_{search} improves the SER at the cost of increased t_{search} .

IV. COMPARISON

Table 3 summarizes the main figures-of-merit of the proposed TCAM as compared to state-of-the-art alternatives. For the sake of a fair comparison, all the considered designs were analyzed under the same simulation conditions (144-bit word CAM, DMTJ-based cells, 28 nm FDSOI node, 1000 MC samples, and 3 σ corners). Due to the above conservative assessment, reported data for competitors present worse results than those shown in the respective papers. Differently from prior works where write operation figures-of-merit are not reported, we have included them mainly because applications such as associative

FIGURE 8. Layout of the proposed 10T2DMTJs NV-TCAM cell. At the right is the 3D hybrid CMOS/MTJ process, where MTJs are placed between Metal-3 (M3) and Metal-4 (M4) [8]. V_{search} search signal is loaded onto the BL/SL lines.

processors comprise of frequent write and compare/search operations [11], [14], [15], [32].

Our design exhibits the lowest SER and the lowest search and write energy, at the expense of the search time. However, the search time still remains in the sub-nanosecond range, which is suitable for multiple applications, including associative processors and approximate matching applications [5], [14], [32]. Specifically, the proposed design achieves the SER and write/search energy improvements of $3.8 \times$ and $-73\%/ -79\%$, respectively, compared to the best state-of-the-art NV-TCAM solution [8]. The obtained advantage in terms of SER is dependent of the chosen evaluation timeframe. In fact, if the evaluation timeframe increases to 1 ns, the SER gets worse becoming about the 7.3%. Discussed results are achieved with a very competitive cell area of about $2 \mu\text{m}^2$, which is about $2 \times$ smaller than the less area hungry design.

According to experimental data reported in [33], an endurance of around 10^6 writing cycles has been observed in p-MTJ devices operating at 300 K, 1 V, and with a write pulse width of 10 ns. Since our NV-TCAM cell operates at V_{DD} of about 1 V during write operations and at about half V_{DD} during search operations, it is reasonable to suppose that our proposal should mitigate reliability issues regarding the breakdown of DMTJs, thus ensuring improved endurance in comparison to other NV-TCAM designs that use the same operating voltage for both write and search.

TABLE 3. Figures of merit of different TCAMs under the same simulation conditions (28 nm FDSOI, 144-bit word TCAM, 1000 MC samples, 3σ values, & TT-corners).

	16TCAM [34]	9T2MTJ* [9], [35]	10T4MTJ [7]	15T4MTJ [8]	10T2MTJ (This work)
Technology	28 nm				
Non-Volatile	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES
WER	–	1×10^{-7}			
Word Size	144				
V_{DD} (V)	1.05				
SER	0	51%	28%	8.7%	2.3%
t_{search} (ns)	0.385	0.314	0.92	0.142	0.616
E_{search} (fJ)	38.33	1673	296.2	110.9	23.03
E_{search} (fJ/bit/search)	0.266	11.6	2.06	0.770	0.160
V_{write} (V)	1.05				
V_{search} (V)	1.05				0.45
t_{write} (ns)	few ps	5.86	5.71	5.58	6.61
E_{write} (pJ/bit/write)	0.153	0.17	0.34	0.14	0.08
Cell Area (μm^2)	8.57	4.13	6.69	8.07	2.07

*Note that the circuit solution by Vicuña et al. [35] and that of Matsunaga, et al. [9] are topologically identical, only differing in terms of storage devices (i.e., DMTJs for [35] and SMTJs for [9]). For our comparison, the DMTJ-based circuit topology was considered.

The cell layout and the scheme of the 3D hybrid CMOS/MTJ process suitable for the proposed 10T2DMTJs NV-TCAM cell is shown in Fig. 8.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a DMTJ-based NV-TCAM design based on a voltage divider structure and a dynamic-logic sensing network. The design was evaluated under exhaustive Monte Carlo simulations considering 3σ variation. Our design outperforms its competitors in terms of write and search energy and search error rate by $3.8 \times$, 79% and 73%, respectively, while providing a $4 \times$ smaller cell area. These benefits come at the cost of increased search time; however, this still remains in the sub-nanosecond range. Thanks to the considerably reduced write energy, the proposed design is suitable not only for conventional TCAM applications, but also for associative processor applications like in-memory deep learning processors, where write is as frequent as compare operation.

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